

Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from an excavation at Padholm MKH 1967.

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Samples from two timbers found during excavations at Padholm MKH 1967, were submitted for dendrochronological analysis. The results of this analysis are described in this report.

It was expected that the timbers derived from the Early Roman Iron Age. Initially the dendrochronological analysis failed to confirm a dating for either timber. So sub-samples for C14 were extracted, from each sample, of the outermost rings. These were dated at Poznań Radiocarbon Laboratory, and the C14 demonstrated that the two timbers are from very different events. The oak post x468 grew in the 5th millennium BC while the oak log x467 is from the first millennium BC.

MKH1967X468 Poz-154665 6000 ± 40 BP

MKH1967X467 Poz-154664 2440 ± 35 BP

The calibrated dates, using OxCal v4.4.4 by Bronk Ramsey (2009) and the calibration curve IntCal20 from Reimer *et al* (2020), are shown in fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Padholm MKH 1967. The calibration of the C14 datings are illustrated for each sample (grey), and the dendrochronological position of the dated samples (blue and green) are also shown.

This led to a re-evaluation of the dendrochronological results.

Two tentative dating positions had been identified, and these are coincident with the findings of the C14 analysis. The oak post x468 (E049001a) contains 201 tree-rings, all heartwood, and a position for this covers the period 5147-4947 BC. The tree-ring curve correlates with a prehistoric chronology built by Kjeld Christensen with a *t*-value of 4.72 (table 1). In isolation this would not be a significant correlation but given the C14 result, it is very probably correct. Accounting for missing sapwood the felling of this tree therefore took place after c. 4931 BC (fig. 1).

Padholm sample	t-value	Master chronology
E049001a x468 5147-4947 BC	4.72	w9mm0006 Moseeg DK 6 6132-4456 BC (Christensen 2007 & pers comm)
E049002a x467 967-717 BC	6.48	w9mm0005 Moseeg DK 5 2320-402 BC (Christensen 2007 & pers comm)

Table 1. Padholm MKH 1967. Correlation between the two samples from Padholm and the relevant prehistoric chronologies.

The oak log x467 (E049002a) contains 251 tree-rings, all heartwood, and a position for this covers the period 967-717 BC. The tree-ring curve correlates with a prehistoric chronology built by Kjeld Christensen with a *t*-value of 6.48 (table 1). In isolation this would not be a significant correlation but given the C14 result, it is very probably correct. Accounting for missing sapwood the felling of this tree therefore took place after c. 701 BC (fig. 1).

Methodology

Measuring and analysis of the material is carried out using the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) in which the calculation of the *t*-value ("t-test") "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is embedded. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are consulted. A sapwood average for Northern Germany (ca. 20 sapwood years (-5+10) (Hollstein 1980)) is used for estimating the felling date for the trees that the dated oak samples come from.

Literature

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Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Ave. ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
MKH1967 Padholm											
E049001a	MKH1967 Padholm Vonsild A5575 X468 QUSP	201	5147BC	4947BC	G	0	N	O	H1	83.54	after 4931BC
E049002a	MKH1967 Padholm Vonsild A2246 x2247 X467 QUSP	251	967BC	717BC	G	0	N	O	H1	78.60	after 701BC
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak. PISY = <i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix sp.</i> , spruce/larch. ABAL = <i>Abies sp.</i> , fir. FASY = <i>Fagus sp.</i> , beech											
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